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The use of historical cartographic materials and contemporary lidar models to determine changes in terrain relief in hard coal mining area (Bytomka Catchment, Southern Poland)

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Abstract— The subject of the research was to determine the changes in the terrain that occurred in the Bytomka catchment area under the influence of mining anthropopressure. The research used various source materials. These were archival cartographic materials - Prussian topographic maps from the 19th century and Polish topographic maps from the end of the 20th century. Terrain models for two periods were created on the basis of these maps. The model from the end of the 19th century presented an almost natural terrain (pre-industrial) in the study area, while the model from the end of the 20th century presented the terrain after more than 100 years of mining activity. Additionally, in order to illustrate contemporary changes in the terrain, lidar models from 2011 and 2021 were used. Mining activities, carried out using the deep methods, led to a number of changes on the surface of the terrain, such as: a decrease in the average absolute height, the formation of no-drain depressions (sedimentary basins), changes in the course of the watershed, or an increase in denivelation range.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Bytomka catchment area is located in the southern part of Poland in the Silesian Upland. In geological terms, it is the area of the Upper Silesian Coal Basin (USCB). The Upper Silesian Coal Basin is one of the largest mining areas in Europe. Its area is approximately 7,000 km² and stretches across southern Poland (Silesia Mountains, Lesser Poland) and northeastern Bohemia (Czech Silesia). The history of hard coal mining here dates back to the 16th century, but its dynamic development began in the mid-19th century [1]. For over 150 years, mining was one of the main factors determining the economic development of this area, contributing to the influx of people and the development of settlement units. It was also a factor that had a very strong impact on the natural relief of the USCB. The dynamic development of

coal mining, especially in the 20th century, contributed to the formation of some of the largest subsidence basins in Europe [2,3]. These forms are characteristic of mining areas where mining is carried out using the roof collapse method (without the use of backfill filling the post-mining voids). The lowering of the land surface leads not only to the formation of new forms of relief, which are sedimentation depressions or local depressions of the terrain changing the longitudinal profiles of river valleys, but also to the formation of so-called mining damage, i.e. damage to buildings, communication infrastructure, or the development of floodlands and wetlands in agricultural areas [4,5]. The Bytomka catchment is located in an area where intensive mining activity has been carried out since the end of the 19th century. The peak of mining exploitation occurred in the second half of the 20th century, and since the turn of the 20th and 21st centuries, due to the decreasing profitability of extraction, subsequent mines have been closed. Currently, there is one active coal mine within the boundaries of the study area. The aim of this study was to determine the extent to which long-term mining activity has influenced changes in the terrain in the area of the catchment selected for research.

II. STUDY AREA AND RESEARCH METHODS

The Bytomka is a small river draining the western part of the Silesian Upland. Its length is only 19.2 km, and the contemporary catchment area is 142.9 km². It is one of the tributaries of the Kłodnica, which then flows into the Oder.

Several source materials were used in the research. The oldest materials were historical Prussian topographic maps on a scale of 1:25,000 (Messtischblätter) made in the late 19th century. The terrain shown on these maps reflects the natural (pre-industrial) state - at the time they were made, mining activities (hard coal mining) were in the early stages of development, and therefore the area occupied by landforms related to mining activities was limited to small areas. These maps were made by qualified military cartographers. They can be used for measurements and show relatively small errors compared to contemporary materials - the vertical accuracy of the terrain representation on the maps is up to several meters [6].

In order to determine the absolute height of the research area at the end of the 20th century, Polish topographic maps at a scale of 1:10,000 were used. Historical Prussian maps were rectified to the contemporary coordinate system using the affine method, using several dozen reference points (churches, crossroads). Based on the contour intervals on both sets of maps, two digital terrain models were created, which aimed to recreate the relief from the end of the 19th century (pre-industrial period) and the end of the 20th century, with the contour intervals adjusted to the maximum accuracy of the Prussian maps (accuracy of 1.5

meters). Using simple raster map algebra, changes in the relief that occurred from 1883 to 1994 were determined. The maximum vertical error in this case was determined at the level of ± 1.5 m. The research used measurement data of terrain configuration reconnaissance using lasers (Light Detection and Ranging, LIDAR) [7] conducted as part of airborne laser scanning (ALS) [8]. Data from remote sensing reconnaissance were used to create a digital terrain model (DTM), which is a representation of the shape of the topographic surface after filtering out other cover elements. Two LIDAR models showing relief in 2011 and 2021 were used to trace the changes in relief taking place until 2021. Similarly, as with maps, relief at both points in time was compared using simple raster map algebra. The lidar models used in work are very accurate terrain imaging made using laser scanning. In the case of the juxtaposition of the two LIDAR models, the maximum vertical error was ± 0.3 m (with horizontal errors not exceeding 1 m). In addition, after the LIDAR models had been adjusted, they were compared with the models produced on the basis of both sets of maps, which provided information on how relief changed throughout the study period from 1883 to 2021, as well as from 1994 to 2011 and from 1994 to 2021. Modern terrain models have been generalized to an accuracy comparable to that achieved through the digitization of historical maps, with results presented using contour lines depicting subsidence.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

According to topographic maps from the end of the 19th century, the maximum absolute height in the Bytomka catchment area was 328 meters above sea level, and the minimum was 220 meters above sea level. The average elevation was 269.7 meters above sea level, and the height difference was 108 meters. However, at the end of the 20th century, both the maximum, average and minimum height of the terrain in the study area decreased. The maximum height was then 327.1 meters above sea level, the minimum height was 217.4 meters above sea level, and the average was 265.9 meters above sea level. However, the height difference increased to 109.7 meters. The reason for the changes in height were land subsidence occurring in the eastern part of the study area (Fig.1). In this part of the catchment area, hard coal mining was developed by underground methods at the end of the 19th century. Its dynamic development, especially from the end of the 19th century to the end of the 20th century, led to the creation of a number of landforms such as: extensive subsidence basins, sinkholes (concave forms) and spoil heaps and mounds (convex forms). Extraction of hard coal using roof collapse methods (without the use of backfill filling the post-mining voids) led to the creation of extensive subsidence basins and,

consequently, to changes in altitude relations in the Bytomka catchment area. The analysis of terrain models made on the basis of topographic maps from the end of the 19th and 20th centuries shows that the surface of the catchment area in the period from 1883 to 1994 decreased by an average of 3.8 meters, which gives an average anthropogenic denudation index of about 3.4 cm/year. The consequence of the impact of mining activities was not only the decrease in the surface of the area in the eastern part of the catchment area, but also changes in the course of the watershed (Fig.1). During this period, the catchment area decreased by 7.1 km². Due to the development of a vast undrained area in the northeastern part of the study area. Extensive and deep subsidence basins also developed in the catchment area itself, leading to the development of undrained areas.

According to the analysis of the lidar model performed in 2011, the maximum absolute height in the catchment area was 327.3 meters, and the minimum 215.7 meters above sea level, with an average of 265.8. Compared to the situation at the end of the 20th century, there was a slight decrease in the average height of the terrain (0.1 meters) and an increase in the denivelation to 111.6 meters. The slight changes in the average absolute height of the terrain resulted primarily from a much shorter period and from the fact that at the end of the 20th century, the mining plants operating in this area began to be gradually liquidated. Waste rock mounds, which were used to level subsidence basins or, for example, as material for road construction, also began to disappear from the landscape. It should be emphasized, however, that the model based on the 1994 topographic map is much less accurate than the 2011 lidar model and does not include many smaller landforms (such as road or railway embankments, etc.).

The analysis of the model performed in 2021 shows that in the decade 2011-2021 the altitude relations changed very little. The maximum height was then 327.5 meters above sea level (an increase of 0.2 m), the minimum 214.7 meters above sea level (a decrease of 1.0 meter), and the average height 265.8 meters (no change in the period 2011-2021).

Figure 1. Changes in terrain elevation in the study area from 1883 to 2021: 1 - watershed in 2021, 2 - watershed in 1883, 3 - streams, 4 - changes in ground height in metres.

IV. CONCLUSION

By using various source materials, historical topographic maps and lidar models, it was possible to reconstruct absolute height changes in the area subject to long-term mining anthropopressure. As a result of long-term activities related to hard coal mining using deep methods (without filling post-mining voids), extensive land subsidence occurred, which covered a total surface of about 76 km², including the eastern part of the study area. This led to the formation of deep subsidence basins, the maximum depths of which exceeded 35 meters, thus causing a decrease in the average absolute height in the area of the studied catchment, as well as a change in the course of watersheds and the formation of no-drain areas. The volume of subsidence calculated on the basis of changes in the average absolute elevation of the terrain for the period 1883-2021 amounted to 567.0 million cubic meters.

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